

OOPS! Evaluation Results

Id	Error	Cases	Level	Reason
1	P05- Defining wrong inverse relationships	1	Critical	This pitfall arises when inverse properties are incorrectly defined.
2	P08- Missing annotations	1	Minor	This issue indicates that one or more ontology elements (classes, properties, or individuals) lack annotations such as rdfs:label, rdfs:comment, or dc:description.
3	P11- Missing domain or range in properties	2	Important	This problem occurs when object or data properties lack explicit domain or range declarations.
4	P13- Inverse relationships not explicitly declared	2	Minor	This pitfall reflects the absence of explicit owl:inverseOf declarations between properties that conceptually represent inverse relations.
5	P19- Defining multiple domains or ranges in properties	2	Critical	This issue occurs when a property is assigned multiple domains or ranges without using union constructs.